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D13.1 Dissemination and Communication Plan

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Table of Contents

TABLE OF CONTENTS	5
LIST OF FIGURES	6
LIST OF TABLES	6
ABBREVIATIONS	7
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	8
1 INTRODUCTION	9
1.1 THE VITALISE PROJECT	9
1.2 DESCRIPTION OF “WP13 DISSEMINATION, EXPLOITATION, OPENNESS AND SUSTAINABILITY”	9
1.3 PURPOSE AND SCOPE	9
1.4 STRUCTURE OF THE DELIVERABLE.....	10
1.5 RELATION TO OTHER WPS AND TASKS	10
2 DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION STRATEGY	12
2.1 WHY TO DISSEMINATE AND COMMUNICATE.....	12
2.2 TO WHOM TO DISSEMINATE AND COMMUNICATE	14
2.2.1 <i>Health and wellbeing Living Labs</i>	15
2.2.2 <i>Research infrastructures</i>	15
2.2.3 <i>Academia and researchers from different disciplines</i>	16
2.2.4 <i>Healthcare providers</i>	17
2.2.5 <i>Public institutions</i>	17
2.2.6 <i>Policy makers</i>	17
2.3 WHAT TO DISSEMINATE AND COMMUNICATE	18
2.4 WHEN TO DISSEMINATE AND COMMUNICATE.....	20
2.5 HOW TO DISSEMINATE	21
3 DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION TOOLS & CHANNELS	24
3.1 VISUAL IDENTITY	24
3.1.1 <i>Logo</i>	24
3.1.2 <i>Document and presentation templates</i>	25
3.1.3 <i>VITALISE brochure</i>	26
3.1.4 <i>VITALISE poster</i>	26
3.1.5 <i>Project presentation</i>	26
3.1.6 <i>Press-Releases</i>	27
3.1.7 <i>Newsletters</i>	27
3.2 WEBSITE	28
3.3 SOCIAL MEDIA CHANNELS	29
3.4 VIDEOS.....	31
3.5 PUBLICATIONS	31
3.6 EVENTS DATABASE	32
3.7 COMMUNITY OF STAKEHOLDERS	33
3.8 NETWORK OF RESEARCHERS	34
3.9 SYNERGIES.....	34
3.10 EVENTS ORGANISED BY THE PROJECT	36
3.11 VITALISE ADVISORY BOARD	37
4 SUMMARY OF DISSEMINATION ACTIONS	38
5 MONITORING AND EVALUATION	40
5.1 MONITORING PROCEDURE: REPORTING AND FEEDBACK.....	41
5.2 VITALISE GUIDE ON DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION	43
APPENDICES	44
APPENDIX 1: VITALISE FIRST PRESS RELEASE	44

List of Figures

FIGURE 1: VITALISE PROJECT METHODOLOGY AND WORK PLAN	11
FIGURE 2: THE EU EMBLEM.....	13
FIGURE 3: VITALISE DISSEMINATION TIME STAGES	21
FIGURE 4: VITALISE NETWORK IN NUMBERS	22
FIGURE 5: VITALISE LOGO (VERTICAL AND HORIZONTAL).....	24
FIGURE 6: VITALISE PRESENTATIONS TEMPLATE.....	25
FIGURE 7: VITALISE DOCUMENTS TEMPLATE	26
FIGURE 8: SLIDES FROM VITALISE PROJECT PRESENTATION.....	27
FIGURE 9: VITALISE FIRST PRESS RELEASE	27
FIGURE 10: VITALISE NEWSLETTER SIGN UP FORM.....	28
FIGURE 11: VITALISE PROJECT WEBSITE HOMEPAGE	29
FIGURE 12: VITALISE WEBSITE STRUCTURE	29
FIGURE 13: VITALISE SOCIAL MEDIA ACCOUNTS	30
FIGURE 14: VITALISE DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES REPORT	42

List of Tables

TABLE 1: VITALISE PROJECT OUTCOMES TO DISSEMINATE	18
TABLE 2: LIST OF SCIENTIFIC JOURNALS FOR PUBLICATIONS	32
TABLE 3: VITALISE PRELIMINARY EVENTS DATABASE	33
TABLE 4: PRELIMINARY LIST OF PROJECTS RELATED TO VITALISE	35
TABLE 5: LIST OF EVENTS ORGANISED BY VITALISE CONSORTIUM	37
TABLE 6: VITALISE SPECIFIC COMMUNICATION MEASURES AND TARGETS	38

Abbreviations

EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
H2020	Horizon 2020 Program of the European Commission
WP	Work Package
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
AB	Advisory Board

Executive summary

This document (D13.1 Dissemination and Communication Plan) describes the dissemination and communication plan of VITALISE project, elaborating on the incentives, objectives, methodology, tools, channels and evaluation methods identified as most suitable within the framework of “WP13 Dissemination, Exploitation, Openness and Sustainability”. The Dissemination and Communication Plan aims to ensure the visibility, dissemination and exploitation of the progress and findings of VITALISE across the project target groups and audiences, aiming at creating awareness about the existence of VITALISE, its objectives, progress and results.

In order for the dissemination planning and methodology to be effective, it is important to lay its foundations on the profiles of the target audiences and formulate the communication content into coherent messages. For this reason, this plan provides further details on how the consortium intends to identify, mobilise and engage with stakeholder groups and its means of doing so. The Dissemination and Communication Plan also covers:

- Benefits and results delivered to stakeholders;
- Messages we want to deliver to each for the stakeholder groups;
- Activities that will best ensure the involvement of stakeholders;
- The way to ensure interested stakeholders understand the benefits of the results and access and exploit project results;
- Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) to evaluate the dissemination activities' effectiveness;
- A timeline about what needs to be achieved and when.

The most appropriate channels and communication characteristics for each target group are defined in detail to guide all consortium partners and support communication of the project. The instruments to reach VITALISE stakeholder groups focus on the press, event participation and active online presence (website, social media). Additionally, to ensure effective communication the team will create a GDPR-compliant stakeholder communication list, and will use contact management software (e.g., MailChimp) to store personal data relating to those members registered on the project mailing list. The design and production of all the related dissemination materials throughout the duration of the project, including a project website, logo, posters, etc., are also essential for the success of the dissemination strategy.

VITALISE dissemination and communication activities will be implemented under the constant evaluation, reviewing and monitoring of the project's dissemination leader, VILABS. VILABS will also review the dissemination and communication plan's progress in meeting KPIs regularly (every 6 months) to ensure its effectiveness.

Overall, the Dissemination and Communication Plan will set the ground for the future exploitation and sustainability of the project's results, developing a clear understanding of the value stemming from the project outputs.

1 Introduction

1.1 The VITALISE Project

Researchers in the Health and Wellbeing domain need 1) convenient access to research infrastructures, 2) direct engagement of people in order to validate hypotheses, co-design solutions and services, evaluate their feasibility and effectiveness and participate in the translation and mobilization of outcomes and 3) experience from multidisciplinary domains (e.g., healthcare management, assistive technologies, data science) to deal with the complexity of health and wellbeing research.

Over the last few years, Living Labs have emerged as resilient research and innovation infrastructures and have proved to be key to the integration of research and innovation processes in real life settings, focusing primarily on people and their engagement in research procedures. VITALISE opens up Living Lab Infrastructures as a means to facilitate and promote research activities in the Health and Wellbeing domain in Europe and beyond by enabling in-person Transnational Access to 17 Living Lab research infrastructures and by supporting remote digital access to datasets (Virtual Access) of rehabilitation, transitional care and everyday life activities through harmonized processes and common tools. VITALISE will design and develop ICT tools for shared access of similar devices and applications used across Living Labs, as well as for collecting, storing and sharing datasets. Lastly, VITALISE will invest in the development of Training methods towards the wider understanding and valorisation of Living Lab methodologies in the research community.

1.2 Description of “WP13 Dissemination, Exploitation, Openness and Sustainability”

“WP13 Dissemination, Exploitation, Openness and Sustainability” describes all the dissemination and communication activities that will take place throughout the project aiming to maximize its impact and ensure the visibility, dissemination and exploitation of the progress and findings of VITALISE across the project target groups and audiences. Through the Dissemination and Communication Plan, further details on how the consortium intends to identify, mobilise and engage with stakeholder groups and its means of doing so will be provided.

Overall, the objectives of WP13 are:

- To raise awareness within participants, target groups and the European society at large about the existence of VITALISE, its objectives, progress and results.
- To ensure that the project’s results reach the various target groups and the European Society, thus stimulating a dialogue about Health and Wellbeing Living Labs.
- To update stakeholders with news and improvements related to VITALISE.
- To plan and verify the exploitation potential and added value of all VITALISE exploitable outcomes during and beyond the end of the project progress.
- To co-design and co-develop sustainable business models out of the main VITALISE project results that will target on the sustainability of VITALISE after the end of the project.

1.3 Purpose and Scope

This document, “D13.1 Dissemination and Communication Plan” is the first outcome of “Task 13.1 Dissemination and Communication plan” and aims to present the plan of the dissemination and communication strategy that VITALISE employs to achieve promotion and impact of the project outcomes to the targeted audiences. In order to define the most appropriate methods to disseminate and communicate the project, this document presents the objectives, focal points, channels and tools that will be utilized within the dissemination strategy of the project to reach all identified target audiences.

In this context, this deliverable:

- describes the VITALISE dissemination approach;
- elaborates on the goals of the plan;
- describes the tools and channels that will be used;
- identifies stakeholders that constitute the project's target audience and the intended engagement with these target groups;
- provides the monitoring and evaluation procedures for the dissemination strategy.

The VITALISE Dissemination and Communication Plan is intended to be a live document, meaning that it will be regularly assessed and updated based on the forthcoming project's achievements and contributions from partners. The responsibilities of the consortium partners are also clarified, along with guidelines and suggestions, under the continuous monitoring of the WP13 leader.

1.4 Structure of the deliverable

"D13.1 Dissemination and Communication Plan" involves five chapters that discuss and analyse in detail different thematic topics concerning the VITALISE dissemination and communication strategy. More specifically:

- The **first chapter** of the document is introductory, aiming to provide some basic information regarding the VITALISE project, a brief description of "WP13 Dissemination, Exploitation, Openness and Sustainability", the purpose and scope of the deliverable, its structure and relation to other WPs and tasks.
- The **second chapter** of the deliverable analyses the dissemination and communication strategy of the project, discussing important topics about why the partnership needs to disseminate and communicate the project, the target audiences, a specific timeline about what needs to be communicated and when, as well as some guidelines to recall when carrying out dissemination activities.
- The **third chapter** of the document analyses the dissemination and communication tools and channels that are going to be exploited within the framework of VITALISE's dissemination strategy. More specifically, it discusses the project's visual identity (logo, document and presentation templates, flyers, posters, etc.), the VITALISE website, the social media channels, the project's events database, the intended community of stakeholders and network of researchers, as well as the targeted synergies.
- The **fourth chapter** is a summary of the dissemination actions, tools, channels and objectives that were analysed in the previous sections.
- The **fifth chapter** of the deliverable refers to the monitoring and evaluation tools that will be utilised for implementing the project's dissemination and communication strategy, as well as the expected results.

1.5 Relation to other WPs and tasks

The broader goal of the dissemination and communication strategy of VITALISE is to raise awareness in diverse environments and ensure that its projected results will be leveraged by the identified stakeholder groups. Hence, the overall project Dissemination and Communication Plan is directly associated with the outcomes of the different WPs in the project since they feed useful content to be disseminated from the partnership.

Figure 1: VITALISE Project Methodology and Work Plan

Figure 1 depicts the VITALISE project methodology and work plan. The scheme demonstrates the horizontal interaction of “WP13 Dissemination, Exploitation, Openness and Sustainability” with the rest of the WPs of the project. Therefore, the dissemination and communication activities interact with and support all project activities that take place within the context of other work packages.

2 Dissemination and communication strategy

The dissemination and communication activities of VITALISE aim to raise awareness regarding the project among the target audiences of specific stakeholder groups that constitute project's community, thus maximising the outreach of the project activities and results. The goal is to ensure that adequate information and key messages are shared with the appropriate audiences on a timely basis utilising the most effective channels and methods.

To achieve this, VITALISE's dissemination and communication strategy needs to answer some key questions that will guide the dissemination and communication activities of the consortium. These questions are:

- **Why** to disseminate and communicate?
- **What** to disseminate and communicate?
- **When** to dissemination and communicate?
- **To whom** to disseminate and communicate?
- **How** to disseminate and communicate?

The following sub-chapters elaborate on the enlisted questions to provide a detailed overview about the VITALISE dissemination and communication plan.

2.1 Why to disseminate and communicate

All VITALISE project partners are involved in the dissemination and communication efforts and need to engage in dissemination activities to foster awareness, transfer key messages and achieve impact, especially in their own countries and communities. The rationale for a carefully designed dissemination and communication plan is based on the requirements for attaining the maximum possible impact for the project by reaching a variety of audiences and communicating the right message to the right audience, as derived from the dissemination objectives, the contractual obligations and the project's overall goals.

Main Objectives. The objectives of the VITALISE dissemination and communication strategy are formed to jointly satisfy specific needs, identified as:

- **Engagement of stakeholders:** to achieve its ends, VITALISE has to seek to engage with a body of third parties which will act as potential contributors to the development, evaluation, uptake and exploitation of its outcomes and encourage their participation to project's actions on a systematic and regular basis.
- **Awareness building:** to secure a certain level of impact and promote a European collaborative approach on research and innovation, it is crucial for VITALISE to work towards the cultivation of its awareness status in the diverse environments of the target audiences.
- **Feedback extraction:** as VITALISE is a multidisciplinary project, it is expected to produce a series of reports and tools. It is purposeful to disseminate such materials towards target audiences that will grasp such knowledge and provide valuable critical insights about it.
- **Collaboration fostering:** as VITALISE is operating in a cross-European and multidisciplinary level, there are multiple entities which would be of high influence on the project in terms of creating a network of organisations that operate on the same level and domain.

Contractual obligations. According to contractual obligations stated in the project's Grant Agreement, the VITALISE consortium should disseminate and communicate the progress and findings of the project to identified stakeholder groups and the public in general. More specifically:

- Article 29.1 of the grant agreement, "Obligation to disseminate results", states that: "*Unless it goes against their legitimate interests, each beneficiary must - as soon as possible - 'disseminate' its results by disclosing them to the public by appropriate means (other than those resulting from protecting or exploiting the results), including in scientific publications (in any medium)*".

- Article 38.1.1 of the grant agreement, “Obligation to promote the action and its results”, clarifies that: “*The beneficiaries must promote the action and its results, by providing targeted information to multiple audiences (including the media and the public) in a strategic and effective manner*”.

It should also be noted that in Article 29.4 of the Grant Agreement “Information on EU funding — Obligation and right to use the EU emblem”, it is stated that “*Unless the Commission requests or agrees otherwise or unless it is impossible, any dissemination of results (in any form, including electronic) must (a) display the EU emblem and (b) include the following text: “This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101007990.”*”

Figure 2: The EU emblem

T13.1 goals. The VITALISE Dissemination and Communication Plan is essential to ensure the visibility, dissemination and exploitation of the progress and findings of the project across the identified target groups and audiences and drive stakeholders’ engagement with the project and its results. Within the VITALISE project duration it is important to deliver the highest possible impact to stakeholders inside and outside the project partnership and ensure that:

- a. the project outputs can be fully exploited and the facilitation of the sustainability of the main VITALISE results is boosted;
- b. the knowledge gained through the project will be made available to all interested stakeholders;
- c. the key elements of excellence of the project can be reused and replicated in other projects, becoming a reference point triggering further developments in the field and beyond;
- d. the project will reach policy-makers to contribute improving future policies;
- e. the benefits that the project outcomes will bring to society are well pointed out.

Project objectives. VITALISE Dissemination and Communication Plan aims to also assist the successful implementation of several macro-objectives of the project. More specifically, the plan takes into account the following objectives of the project:

- **O#1 “Attract external researchers (open calls in WP11) to submit study ideas for Transnational Access in different research Infrastructures”:** An effective “Dissemination and Communication Plan” can guarantee the effective outreach of new external researchers (Task 13.2) to submit study ideas for Transnational Access in different research Infrastructures, within the framework of the open calls taking place in “WP11 Calls for ideas and proposals, experiment selection”. The KPIs set out for this specific objective are more than 100 researchers recruited for trans-national access (KPI1.1) and more than 200 researchers granted for virtual access (KPI1.2).
- **O#8 “Develop material and educational programs for new researchers that would like to use Living Lab services and procedures as well as to train new or existing Health and Wellbeing Living Labs on how to harmonize with VITALISE developed standards for services and procedures harmonization”:** An effective “Dissemination and Communication Plan” can facilitate the outreach of these materials to a wide number of new researchers that would like to use the Living Lab services and procedures.
- **O#9 “Develop fast track training program for researchers applying for Transnational and Virtual Access in the provided research infrastructures”:** Similarly, through the dissemination and communication activities of the project, new researchers can be attracted to the fast-track training program that will be developed for researchers applying for Transnational and Virtual Access in the provided research infrastructures.

- **O#10 “Organise and run summer schools for young researchers that will be satellite events of ENOLL’s flagship yearly event, Digital Living Lab Days”:** By undertaking efficacious dissemination and communication activities, the attraction of a total number of fifty (50) young researchers joining VITALISE summer schools (KPI10.2) can be facilitated.
- **O#11 “Design and ran an Acceleration Bootcamp that will enhance the researchers’ business strategy and/or tactics”:** In the same direction, to attract a total number of fifty (50) researchers joining the VITALISE Acceleration Bootcamp (KPI11.1), pertinent and targeted messages need to be disseminated to the targeted audience.
- **O#12 “Publish common state of the art research protocols and results that support the innovation and scientific potential of Health and Wellbeing Living Labs”:** The effective dissemination of these results highly depends on the effectiveness of the project’s dissemination and communication strategy.
- **O#13 “Foster a culture of co-operation between research infrastructures, scientific communities, industries and other stakeholders to help develop a more efficient and attractive European Research Area”:** Effective communication is key for achieving co-operation among these communities and an important focal point for VITALISE Dissemination and Communication Plan.
- **O#15 “Enhance communication between academia and industry, policy and the public”:** VITALISE focuses on enhancing the communication between academia and industry, policy and the public, which can be facilitated through synergetic effects derived from the dissemination and communication activities of the project. The goal is to achieve more than ten (10) meetings with industry at regional level and European level (KPI5.1), more than twenty (20) meetings with policy makers at regional level and European level (KPI5.2) and include Living Labs in the next ESFRI Roadmap version (KPI5.3).
- **O#16 “Develop and continuously improve standards for Health and Wellbeing Living Lab procedures”:** Communication and dissemination activities can foster the wider participation of target audiences in the Harmonization Body meetings, which will be open to the public. The aim is to hold five (5) or more of these meetings (KPI6.3).
- **O#17 “Establish a Harmonization Body that will meet every six months in order to reconsider the existing standards”:** To attain the targeted number of twenty (20) or more living labs, beyond the consortium members, joining the Harmonization Body meetings (KPI7.1), as well as twenty (20) or more researchers joining the open events and Harmonization body meetings (KPI7.2), there is a need to effectively disseminate relevant content to the targeted audience.

The dissemination and communication activities of the project will be taking place throughout the whole 36-month project duration, to guarantee that all relevant stakeholders receive updates, news and improvements related to VITALISE.

2.2 To whom to disseminate and communicate

In order to be effective, the project’s dissemination and communication strategy is selective about the choice of audience and strategic about its approach to that audience. VITALISE Dissemination and Communication Plan targets various stakeholders from different organisational, economic, and social contexts, i.e., academia (researchers, universities, research organisations), public institutions (at the level of cities, regions and local, regional, national & European policy), private organisations (start-ups, SMEs, corporations), as well as citizens. More specifically, the core group of stakeholders is comprised of:

- **Health and wellbeing Living Labs;**
- **Research infrastructures;**
- **Academia** (universities, research organizations) and **researchers** from different disciplines (medical and rehabilitation experts, psychologists, neurologists, sociologists, anthropologists, ethicists, health economists and computer scientists);
- **Healthcare providers** (doctors, nurses, rehabilitation professionals, physiotherapists, occupational therapists, etc.);

- **Public institutions** (cities, regions);
- Local, regional, national and European **policy makers**.

Therefore, the final beneficiaries are the extensive and multidisciplinary research community around Health and Wellbeing, as well as the relevant innovation and industry bodies (including but not limited to SMEs and start-ups). Instead of just bringing together interested parties, the objective is to define standard processes and key elements shared among them. This strongly interconnected network consisted of Living Labs, young researchers and SMEs will work together to create new research activities. VITALISE's vision is the sustainability of the community and the maintenance of networking activities beyond the project's lifecycle.

2.2.1 Health and wellbeing Living Labs

Living Labs are research infrastructures that enable research studies to take place in real life environments with the involvement of multiple stakeholders, ensuring strong focus on the end-users, cocreation approaches and enabling innovation. Living Labs have the ability to better integrate the opportunities offered by new ICT concepts and solutions to the specific needs and aspirations of local contexts, cultures, and creativity potentials.

The research community in the Health and Wellbeing domain has invested a great deal of effort in establishing new Living Labs in order to support their research. An important challenge in this line of research is to create trust between researchers and local communities as they evaluate and exploit research results. This has caused the creation of many project-oriented Living Labs that serve specific research purposes and have a lifecycle similar to a projects' duration, thus leading to higher costs, non-optimal use of resources, time and distribution of work and expertise, limited exploitation of research results from local communities.

VITALISE aims to put in place the winning conditions for researchers and communities, fostering innovative, person-centered research by creating a Health and Wellbeing Living Lab ecosystem. To do so, the project interlinks the three biggest Living Lab networks in Europe, in order to cover all the European geographical areas and all the spectrum of the Health and Wellbeing domain. Those three major living lab networks participating in the project are:

- [ENOLL](#) (European Network of Living Labs), with 130 Living Lab members around the world, 41% of which are in the Health and Wellbeing domain;
- [EIT Health Living Labs](#), composed of 56 active Living Labs and an additional 37 that are in the process of joining, all of them in the Health and Wellbeing domain;
- [Forum LLSA](#) comprised of 38 members, all of which in the Health and Wellbeing domain.

The project's main goal is to provide effective and convenient access to Living Lab infrastructures, procedures, and policies for real-life settings for experimentation, engaged involvement of participants, state of the art technology and teams with multidisciplinary expertise beyond these existing networks by building a worldwide Harmonization Board and Body for Health and Wellbeing Living Labs.

2.2.2 Research infrastructures

European researchers need effective and convenient access to the best research infrastructures and engagement of people, in order to conduct research for the advancement of knowledge and technology. VITALISE works on facilitating access to Living Lab research infrastructures and sharing widely the value of Living Labs within the research community. The aim is to reinforce partnerships, integrate on a European scale, and open up key national and regional research infrastructures to all European researchers, from both academia and industry, ensuring their optimal use and joint development.

VITALISE enables in-person Transnational Access to 17 Living Lab research infrastructures and by supporting remote digital access to datasets (Virtual Access) of rehabilitation, transitional care and everyday life activities through harmonized processes and common tools. To create a large thematic Living Lab ecosystem of virtually interconnected research infrastructures in the Health and Wellbeing

domain and make it available to a wider research community, VITALISE's Dissemination and Communication Plan targets research infrastructures to join the ecosystem of virtually interconnected research infrastructures in the Health and Wellbeing domain, through targeted dissemination of messages and networking activities, to foster a culture of co-operation between research infrastructures, scientific communities, industries and other stakeholders, and to help develop a more efficient and attractive European Research Area.

2.2.3 Academia and researchers from different disciplines

VITALISE's Dissemination and Communication Plan targets researchers from multiple disciplines through tailored dissemination activities to engage with the project and utilize its research infrastructures to conduct research in the health and wellbeing domain.

The most relevant groups of researchers identified within the framework of the project are:

- **Cross-discipline researchers:** Researchers from different disciplines (medical and rehabilitation experts, psychologists, neurolinguists, sociologists, anthropologists, ethicists, health economists, computer scientists) to put into action their interdisciplinary and intersectoral projects through pilot testing with diverse populations and methodologies, as well as interpret results with multidisciplinary teams.
- **Engineers/ Information Technology experts:** This category can benefit through technical or technology development, including algorithm development, computing, software and hardware connectivity that is enhanced through user involvement, rapid prototyping targeted in user needs and user-centred design.
- **UI designers:** UI designers can support product/service development in terms of user experience design, encompassing all aspects of the end user's interaction with the products/services.
- **Medical staff** (doctors, nurses, rehabilitation professionals, etc.): This group can exploit the continuous fine-tuning and testing of new medical approaches and methodologies, in constant communication with the targeted patients. Living Labs enable more user-friendly approaches for pilot testing of medical researchers.
- **Living Lab and cocreation theory researchers:** VITALISE facilitates the development of a community of early adopters by co-creating and experimenting and enables them to be identified and trusted by the research community and industry. Through VITALISE they can improve quality and/or quantity of the services and infrastructures within Living Labs and foster synergies among different research groups, thus reducing duplicate work.
- **Psychologists:** Psychologists can assess mental states, perceptual, cognitive, emotional, and social processes and behaviour by experimenting with, and observing, interpreting, and recording how individuals relate to one another and to their environment using Living Labs infrastructures and methodologies.
- **Socio-economists/ Health economists:** This group can measure the economic impact of a solution on society and living conditions through interaction and monitoring of end-users, and advanced policy making capacity.
- **Patient experts:** A key role and function among the Living Lab and all through the innovating process is to ensure relevant and valuable use for the patient. The patient expert is deeply involved in any ergonomic or ethno-sociographic approach challenging innovation processes.

Also, researchers from SMEs have an ongoing collaboration with many VITALISE Living Labs in order to test and improve their products. This type of collaboration and research exploitation scheme has already been identified as a sustainability goal of ENoLL and is widely adopted by EIT Health Living Labs and Forum LLSA.

Overall, VITALISE enables researchers from different disciplines will put into action their interdisciplinary and intersectoral projects through pilot testing with diverse populations and methodologies, as well as interpret results with multidisciplinary teams. For this reason, academia and researchers from different disciplines comprise a major stakeholder group for the project.

2.2.4 Healthcare providers

Healthcare professionals and the medical staff (doctors, nurses, rehabilitation professionals, etc.) are a very essential stakeholder group to reach through VITALISE project's dissemination activities. Healthcare professionals can benefit from the project through the continuous fine-tuning and testing of new medical approaches and methodologies, in constant communication with the targeted patients, since Living Labs enable more user-friendly approaches for pilot testing of medical researchers. What is more, healthcare professionals are also a major target audience for the VITALISE Harmonization Body and Harmonization Toolkit.

As an example, the Joint Research Activity for transitional care (JRA2) of the project will study the transit needs of patients. The collected data, coming from ICT monitoring and intervention tools, will be analysed and fused in order to provide higher level interpretable information to healthcare professionals and support their decision for the course of care. A first analysis within the framework of Task 6.3 will be conducted with healthcare professionals from the clinical settings in order to identify the most important information needed to support the transition decision. The expected results (Task 6.4 – Results and analysis) are to create recommendations, coming from both clinical and home settings, that can support the healthcare professionals in decisions about transitional care (e.g., when is the right time to transit, follow-up care, readmission handling).

Overall, healthcare professionals will be able to utilize the pooled infrastructure to acquire state-of-the-art services and data, while at the same time building an extensive multi-stakeholder community around it, forming part of the VITALISE ecosystem. For this reason, they comprise a very essential stakeholder group for VITALISE project.

2.2.5 Public institutions

The VITALISE Dissemination and Communication Plan considers public authorities a very significant stakeholder group for establishing the Harmonization Board and Body for Health and Wellbeing research procedures in Living Labs. Even if common services and procedures are already identified among Living Labs, they are not yet provided in a common agreed way. Public authorities from different Member States hold a key role towards procedures, services and e-infrastructure harmonization.

The main method for engaging public authorities around the project is through networking activities. For example, a key networking event is the Digital Living Lab Days, which is organised every year by ENoLL, and attracts researchers, public authorities, innovators, entrepreneurs, and Living Lab practitioners to exchange knowledge, best practices, methodologies, and tools related to Living Labs and user engagement. The VITALISE consortium will maintain strong bonds with public authorities, by inviting them to events and broadly engaging them with the project.

2.2.6 Policy makers

Policy makers are an essential stakeholder group to establish the VITALISE Harmonization Body and it is considered crucial for the long-term viability and the exploitation of VITALISE to establish a communication channel with the policy makers. VITALISE will invite policy makers at the European level to join the Harmonisation Body meetings and get actively involved in different stages and lifecycles of the project to contribute to the improvement of future policies.

Task 13.4 of the project "Awareness towards the general public and policy makers" focuses merely to the setup and maintenance of an active community of stakeholders including policy makers that will support the validation of the project outcomes and their innovation and sustainability potential and thus will actively contribute to enrich them. The task involves all activities for shaping the VITALISE external community that will participate in the development process (through the provision of feedback). Except for the general dissemination activities, the task involves the organisation of yearly events for presenting VITALISE to key policy makers in Europe. Linking this task with "Task 13.3 VITALISE Innovation Monitoring Systems" is also a business intelligence tool for policy makers to design forthcoming EU-funded collaborative research and innovation programmes.

One of the macro-objectives of VITALISE (O#15) is to enhance communication between academia and industry, policy and the public, aiming at holding at least twenty (20) meetings with policy makers at regional and European level. For this reason, the dissemination and networking activities of the project are highly focused on reaching this specific stakeholder group.

2.3 What to disseminate and communicate

Within the framework of VITALISE project, there are several main project outcomes that have been initially identified as important for dissemination and communication. These outcomes are summarised in Table 1 below.

Table 1: VITALISE Project Outcomes to Disseminate

Outcome	Type	Target audience	Indicator of success
Harmonization Body O#17 (WP2)	Body	Living Lab researchers and practitioners, healthcare professionals, policy makers	Number of body meetings (open to the public): >5 Number of researchers joining the open events and board meetings, beyond the members of the consortium: >20 Number of Living Labs joining the Harmonization Body meetings, beyond the members of the consortium: >20 One (1) sustainability plan is prepared and agreed between the consortium
Standards for Health and Wellbeing Living Lab procedures O#16 (WP2)	Standards	Living Labs, Healthcare professionals, Researchers, Policy Makers	Number of standard versions: >6 Number of KPIs agreed and shared among the Living Labs as standards, monitoring their progress: >15
Panel Management Tool O#7 (T3.7)	ICT tools	Living Labs, Researchers	Registered Living Lab infrastructures: >8 Total number of enrolled participants: >100 One (1) exploitation/business plan focusing on the sustainability and long- term use of the Panel Management system.
VITALISE SDK O#4 (T3.9)	ICT tools	Living Labs, Researchers	Number of supported devices: >4 Number of SDKs designed and develop to enable access to the infrastructure: 2
The VITALISE platform WP3	ICT tools	Living Labs, Researchers	Number of publications certified by the VITALISE platform >5 One (1) exploitation/business plan focusing on the sustainability and

			long- term use of the ICT tools developed.
Harmonization Toolkit (T4.3, T2.2, T2.3, T4.4)	Toolkit	Living Lab researchers and practitioners, healthcare professionals, policy makers	One (1) plan on how to sustain the Toolkit and how to exploit it to a wide target audience.
Summer schools #O10 (T4.1)	Teaching	Young researchers	Total number of young researchers joining VITALISE summer schools: 50 Number of summer schools: 3
Online educational material and training programmes #O8 (T4.2, T4.4)	Training material	Living Labs, Researchers	Number of educational or training programs designed for Living Labs on how to comply with VITALISE along with the corresponding material: >5 (12 hours in total). Number of educational or training programs designed for researchers along with the corresponding material: >3 (6 hours in total) One (1) plan on how to exploit the training material and the online learning programmes to a wide number of target audience.
VITALISE Starting Community (T4.3)	Community	Living Labs, Research infrastructures, Researchers	Number of interconnected research infrastructures beyond the infrastructures provided by the consortium: >4 Number of Living Lab networks join forces towards harmonization / signing the MOU > 3 One (1) sustainability plan is prepared and agreed between the consortium
Postgraduate courses (T4.5)	Teaching	Students, Young researchers	One (1) postgraduate course
Acceleration Bootcamp O#11 (T4.6, T13.3)	Bootcamp	Researchers, Businesses	Total number of researchers joining VITALISE Acceleration Bootcamp: 50
Open calls O#1 (WP11)	Call for proposals	Researchers, Students, Entrepreneurs, Living Lab practitioners	Three (3) open calls for Transnational Access and Virtual Access. Number of researchers recruited for TA access: >100

			Number of researchers recruited for VA: >200
Joint research activities <i>WP8-WP10</i>	Real-life activities	Living Labs, researchers	Number of publications with results from the Joint Research Activities: >3 A sustainability plan is prepared and there is a confirmation from the three pilot activities to keep the JRA activities beyond the end of the project.

2.4 When to disseminate and communicate

To ensure the optimal timing to engage in any sort of dissemination and communication activities, the VITALISE consortium has identified three different time phases for its Dissemination and Communication Plan, where different activities have been assigned to different phases of the project: **early in the project**, **during the project** and **at the end of the project**, with the aim to constantly review and update this strategy according to the progress and new findings of the project.

More specifically:

- **Early in the project** dissemination aims to ensure that the project is addressing the needs of its target groups (especially the researchers and the health and wellbeing Living Labs), and that it is creating awareness and understanding of its activities both within the consortium and among peer groups. A dialogue mechanism with the target groups has already been initiated, enabling them to provide constant feedback during this early phase, mainly via social media, and during the full course of the project.
- **During the project** dissemination is about identifying lessons, particularly in receiving feedback from target groups and stakeholders, and adjusting the project's strategy and developed components in order to maximize effectiveness and efficiency. At this stage it is important to inform the research community and policy makers about the first results of the project and ensure appropriate peer review. Moreover, online marketing activities will ensure wide participation of the target audiences in the project's activities (training programmes, summer schools, community enlargement, research activities in real-life environment).
- **At the end of the project** dissemination will publicize more generally the project's outputs, the lessons learnt, and the benefits gained. The dissemination activities will focus on building up a constituency of support for the project's follow-up activities, as well as on providing evidence to support the exploitation and sustainability of the VITALISE platform, community and the Harmonization body.

Figure 3: VITALISE Dissemination Time Stages

Figure 3 summarizes the three different dissemination phases of the project, as well as the focus of the dissemination and communication activities during each phase.

2.5 How to disseminate

To ensure the effectiveness of the Dissemination and Communication Plan, its foundations should lay on the profiles of the target audiences and communication content should be formulated into coherent messages. Given that the target groups identified cover a wide variety of sectors - from Living Labs to research infrastructures and policy makers - a segmented Dissemination and Communication Plan is needed per target group.

The dissemination and communication plan is based on two levels of strategies for the dissemination of the project's results and its progress:

- The consortium's **overall strategy**, that is the dissemination and communication strategy in which the consortium plans and acts as a whole.
- The **individual strategy of each consortium member**, according to specific type of organisation, infrastructure, role and resources in the project, etc.

The dissemination and communication strategy includes activities that can be divided into internal and external dissemination and communication according to the target audiences they are addressed to.

- The **internal dissemination and communication** includes the instruments and activities that intend to give awareness of the results destined for the consortium members and that are not available to the public in general. This kind of dissemination includes:
 - Project meetings and their resulting reports (physical, virtual)
 - Information exchange e.g., through mailing lists
 - A collaborative workspace document repository
 - Reports, publications, deliverables, etc.
 - On-line collaboration through different means e.g., dissemination report form submission, regular WP and Task related meetings, online documents collaboration, blog posts and comments from partners, doodle polls etc.
- The **external dissemination and communication** refers to activities and means which create awareness of the project's partial and overall results and document the project's progress. The target of those dissemination activities is specific users and interest groups that have been identified above as well as the general public.

VITALISE proposes a **mixed approach** for the effective dissemination of its aims and results, facilitated by a variety of activities, both external and internal and is based on:

- achieving reputation or a “name in the field” by using the media (including social media), speaking at conferences and writing for journals;
- networking – making and sustaining personal contacts and “selling” the project to other people who could prove to be useful contacts;
- capturing the interest of existing initiatives;
- visiting decision-making units and attending to EC workshops and info days; communicating with other project consortiums; and
- being contactable, accessible and creative.

In the VITALISE dissemination and communication strategy social media and the project website play a key role. These dissemination tools act as channels to promote cooperation with other projects and initiatives and generate engagement with key stakeholders through a real feedback channel, which in turn creates valuable assets for future projects. The aforementioned methods and channels will facilitate the sustainability of the project’s solutions and prepare the market for their use.

All consortium members engage in communication activities locally, within the context of their countries to reach European and international audiences. ENoLL, as the project coordinator and also an umbrella organisation for Living Labs, plays a key role in achieving the project’s dissemination goals. Additionally, in line with the proposal’s sex and gender analysis, partners are committed to removing unintentional gender biases in their communication tools and actions, aiming to communicate project activities and results in a **gender-inclusive** way.

Figure 4: VITALISE Network in Numbers

VITALISE interlinks the three biggest Living Lab networks in Europe, [ENoLL](#) (European Network of Living Labs), [EIT Health Living Labs](#), and [Forum LLSA](#), in order to cover all the European geographical areas and all the spectrum of the Health and Wellbeing domain. Those three major living lab networks expand the impact of the Health and Wellbeing Living Lab ecosystem that VITALISE aims to create and boost the dissemination potential of the project. Figure 4 includes qualitative data about the reach of the VITALISE network, according to which ENoLL, EIT Health Living Labs, and Forum LLSA combined give access to:

- **266 members** of their networks;
- A social media community of more than **60000 followers** in total, which already maintains an extensive map and a solid online presence;
- More than **4000 unique newsletter subscribers** in targeted mailing lists for monthly e-newsletters per network;
- More than **25500 unique monthly visitors** on the websites of the three networks;

- More than **twenty (20) organised events** and **fifty (50) participating events** yearly, such as conferences, workshops, exhibitions, virtual meetings and webinars.

Overall, the VITALISE dissemination and communication strategy ensures the visibility, dissemination and exploitation of the progress and findings of VITALISE across the project target groups and audiences. All communication activities, tools and channels are described in detail in the following chapter (Chapter 3).

3 Dissemination and Communication Tools & Channels

3.1 Visual Identity

3.1.1 Logo

An essential part of building a brand is designing and creating a suitable logo to ensure the recognition of the project and communicate its identity to the stakeholder groups and the public in general. For this reason, the VITALISE consortium focused on creating a project logo that reflects the overall concept of the project and its scientific domain of activity, the health and wellbeing sector. Even from the project's title, "Virtual Health and Wellbeing Living Lab Infrastructure", it is made clear that health and wellbeing are two important focal points to be communicated to the public.

Figure 5: VITALISE Logo (Vertical and Horizontal)

Logo colours. The colours of the project's logo are derived from the *Watermelon Crush Color Palette* which can be retrieved here: <https://www.color-hex.com/color-palette/88659>. The main colours of the logo are:

- **Orange:** #ff5a5a
- **Green:** #46ffdb
- **Blue:** #00b5e4
- **Lilac:** #957afc
- **Purple:** #a43981

These colours were selected because of their vibrance, liveliness and energetic effect. The orange colour is associated with joy, happiness, and creativity. The green colour symbolizes life, energy, harmony, and freshness. The colour blue is associated with serenity, stability, and health. Lastly, purple and lilac represent independence, purity and tranquillity.

Typography. The font picked for the logo is "Pirulen Regular", a wide, techno font. The intent was to have a clean, symmetrical font to represent stability and serenity. From an aesthetic perspective, the font has a modern and professional look.

Symbol. The value of Health and Wellbeing Living Labs comes from the fact that they bring research in the authentic and realistic environment of the patient/user. The human-centric and user-centred approach that the project adopts was a very important aspect that project partners decided to communicate through the logo. For this reason, the main symbol of the logo is a person, whose body position creates a movement effect that symbolises positive energy and health. Lastly, using the body figure the shape of a tree is formed, with tree leaves surrounding the top part of the human body. Trees are often used as symbols associated with life, growth and prosperity.

Use. The right use of the project logo ensures the recognition of VITALISE project among targeted stakeholder groups and the public in general. For this reason, it is important that all VITALISE dissemination materials, all documents, presentations in events and conferences and online channels of the project include the project logo in high quality and prominent positioning.

3.1.2 Document and presentation templates

Clean and functional document and presentation templates are essential to achieve harmony and coherence among the many different documents that project partners create throughout the project. In order to deliver a consistent message to all target audiences and facilitate the recognition of the graphical identity of the project, templates for both text documents and presentations were developed and made available to all consortium partners. Those templates include the VITALISE deliverable and document template and the VITALISE presentation template.

The design of the presentations template is aligned with the colours of the logo and the overall aesthetic of the project's graphical identity, with the orange colour being the most dominant. The font used for the template is Helvetica Light.

Figure 6: VITALISE Presentations Template

The documents template is also inspired from the project's graphical identity, with orange being the main design colour. The font picked for the documents template is Arial.

D13.1 Dissemination and Communication Plan

Figure 7: VITALISE Documents Template

3.1.3 VITALISE brochure

On the first year of the project (Year 1) at least one (1) brochure will be developed in English, and will be translated in all partner languages. On the second (Year 2) and third (Year 3) year of the project these materials will be updated according to the progress and advances of the project. Hard copies of the brochure will be made available in order to distribute them to events, where partners participate.

3.1.4 VITALISE poster

On the first year of the project (Year 1) at least one (1) poster will be developed in English and will be translated in all partner languages. On the second (Year 2) and third (Year 3) year of the project the poster will be updated according to the progress and advances of the project. Hard copies of the poster will be prepared for use and distribution to events, where partners participate.

3.1.5 Project presentation

An overall project presentation was created by the project coordinator, ENoLL, in order to present the project's goals, objectives and the project roadmap in all applicable instances. The VITALISE project presentation includes all the important information that create a clear understanding of the project's challenges, impact, concept, activities, procedures and expected results.

Figure 8: Slides from VITALISE project presentation

The project’s overall presentation will be also uploaded on the VITALISE communication channels and will be updated every six months.

3.1.6 Press-Releases

Within the framework of the VITALISE Dissemination and Communication Plan appropriate press releases for announcements concerning the news and advances of the project will be developed.

Figure 9: VITALISE first press release

The partnership has already prepared and shared a first press release regarding the kick-off of the project, which has been included in Appendix 1: VITALISE first press release of the document. Two (2) press releases per partner, regarding the VITALISE development and exploitation will be published in printed and/or electronic media.

3.1.7 Newsletters

During VITALISE project’s duration, six (6) newsletters will be prepared and shared with the subscribed users. Circulating the project newsletter will guarantee target groups are reached not only within the partners’ network but also within a larger community of interested potential users. The newsletter will include news and upcoming events, publications and report project’s achievements. Also, the project will seek regular presence in the already established ENOLL, EIT Health, Forum LLSA newsletters (>4,000 unique subscribers in total). ENOLL circulates a monthly newsletter that summarizes the activities of Living Labs in order to highlight these activities and create networking opportunities. News about VITALISE are going to be included in these newsletters as well.

Figure 10: VITALISE Newsletter sign up form

The project's newsletter sign-up form was created via Mailchimp. MailChimp is a privacy enhancing, GDPR-compliant platform, that allows subscription of interested users to the project's mailing list, while respecting all privacy policies that apply in such instances.

3.2 Website

One of the most essential dissemination and communication tools of VITALISE is the project's website, whose preliminary version launched on the first month (M1) of the project (April 2021). **The website's domain name is vitalise-project.eu**. All the necessary information regarding the progress of the project as well as project news, materials, etc. are uploaded on the project's website.

In particular, the VITALISE website aims at:

- Providing information about the project, its main objectives, description of the produced outputs and knowledge, publications, latest news and upcoming events in which VITALISE will participate, information about project partners with a link to their websites, subscription to project's newsletter, social networks and contact info.
- Presenting information to stakeholders so that they will understand the reasons to get involved and how they can participate in the project's activities.

Figure 111 is a screenshot of the VITALISE website on its current form. The colours of the website match the overall VITALISE graphical identity, with the blue colour being the most dominant on the websites theme. The homepage includes the project logo, the navigation menu of the website, banners with information about the project, a section with the project's latest news, a section with the project's latest Tweets, a newsletter subscription form, a footer with acknowledgement of EU funding, Copyright and Privacy Policy, and links to the VITALISE social media accounts.

Figure 11: VITALISE project website homepage

The current structure of the website pages is depicted in the figure below.

Figure 12: VITALISE website structure

The website is the project’s main portal for communicating project outputs and results with its target audiences. For this reason, it is frequently updated with new content and adjusted according to the project’s advancements and results. To ensure that the dissemination goals of VITALISE are achieved, the partnership, set out measurable KPIs to reach, targeting at least 250 monthly visits for the first year of the project, 500 monthly visits for the second year and more than 750 monthly visits on the final year of the project.

The project will elaborate blogging as a dissemination and communication method that will provide updates in a sustainable frequency about the actions of the consortium members and news related to the project. In their majority, blog entries will refer to either VITALISE’S presence in networking events or its progress of work. For the website’s blog, the target is to create at least one (1) blogpost per month.

3.3 Social Media Channels

VITALISE project’s social media channels are a much-needed part of its dissemination and communication strategy, since they allow engaging stakeholders with the project’s activities and news, while creating a space where interaction is enabled, as well as discussions and provision of feedback. The use of the right social media channels to communicate and disseminate messages regarding the project can significantly help VITALISE increase its reach. Through the use of social media, VITALISE manages to build a steady flow of information towards diverse audiences and sustain a well-informed group of target audiences, which enhances the project’s overall impact.

Figure 13: VITALISE social media accounts

Through Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn, Instagram and YouTube information about the project status and activities are made available to the public. The links of the VITALISE social media channels are the following:

Twitter: <https://twitter.com/VITALISEproject>

LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/vitalise-project/>

Facebook: <https://www.facebook.com/VITALISEproject>

Instagram: <https://www.instagram.com/vitaliseproject/>

YouTube: <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCTvXvgIRLL29-3d9LTulq3A>

Using content that matches the structural affordances of each platform and features SEO characteristics (e.g. relevant hashtags) combined with the partners' already existing accounts, VITALISE accounts are going to be used to increase project's visibility in social networking sites. The use of specific hashtags (#) enables interested parties to be informed about the project's activities and news. Indicatively, the hashtags that are most frequently used for the project's social media posts are:

- #vitalise
- #vitaliseproject
- #livinglab
- #livinglabs
- #health

- #wellbeing
- #harmonisation
- #aha
- #rehabilitation
- #transitionalcare
- #everydaylivingenvironments
- #cocreation
- #H2020
- #EU
- #EUfunded
- #ENoLL
- #research
- #innovation

Regular posts and updates of the social media accounts and a strong presence in these channels is essential for the effective dissemination and communication of the project outcomes. The social networking pages will be updated throughout the whole duration of the project by adding content and news. The KPIs that need to be reached in order to consider the use of these channels successful are:

- **Year 1:** At least one post per week and 500 followers on Twitter, 300 Likes on Facebook and 100 followers on LinkedIn.
- **Year 2:** At least two posts per week (700 followers on twitter, 500 Likes on Facebook and 300 followers on LinkedIn).
- **Year 3:** At least two posts per week (1000 followers on twitter, 700 Likes on Facebook and 500 followers on LinkedIn).

The elaboration of social media as means to dissemination and communication is based on a specific approach. The opted strategy reckons that social media constitute a modern tool, which is constantly updated with news options and features. Hence, such platforms can promote the project and its activities by adapting its communication messages to any given new feature offering new possibilities for reaching relevant audiences.

3.4 Videos

Video content production can be a powerful tool to spread a message in a pertinent and easy to understand manner to a wider audience. There are several multimedia, online tools available to produce informative, high quality video content and share it with a broad audience, thus increase project impact. For this reason, VITALISE will regularly produce video content and share it on its YouTube channel and other social media pages. The content can both be unique, produced for the purposes of disseminating a specific message about project related matters or derived from webinars, courses, live videos, or self-hosted partners' videos. Partners have already published a video on the VITALISE [YouTube](#) channel from the project's kick-off meeting open session, which can be accessed through this link: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=2Sgb910JS1U>.

What is more, two more videos regarding VITALISE will be produced, to promote the project and provide information about the VITALISE community. More specifically:

- the development of the “visual presentation” of the project in the form of a video is estimated to be ready on the 12th month of the project (March 2022).
- the “VITALISE product” video with information about the VITALISE community and the aim to enhance the sustainability of this community, will be prepared on *Year 3* of the project (2023).

3.5 Publications

Publications are a significant element of VITALISE's dissemination strategy, since they constitute a dissemination tool that informs and engages the VITALISE community about the projects'

procedures, methodologies and outcomes. The projected body of reports conducted by project partners, not only fuels the project's development but also facilitates its dissemination planning.

Overall, publications involve two overlapping elements:

- **Deliverable Reports:** A considerable volume of partners work efforts is focused on conducting research and producing reports. This material is valuable in terms of effective dissemination of the project's contribution. The public deliverable reports will be uploaded on an open access repository supported by the European Commission, [Zenodo](https://zenodo.org/). VITALISE project has already established the "VITALISE Project: Virtual Health and Wellbeing Living Lab Infrastructure" Zenodo community, which can be accessed through the following link: <https://zenodo.org/communities/vitaliseproject/?page=1&size=20>.
- **Scientific Publications:** Drawing from the above report material, project partners will be devoted in the creation of scientific articles published in the international scientific literature, when possible. All partners acknowledge their common interest in publishing the knowledge to obtain recognition and to advance the state of knowledge in the field. In this respect, any partner who is considering preparing a publication for a scientific magazine, is strongly encouraged to contact other partners in order to work together in this publication. Especially when the content of the publication is a product of the collective work of the consortium (or of a sub-group of partners), the names of the respective people and partners should appear on the publication. The consortium has drafted a non-exhaustive list of scientific journals where VITALISE partners can publish scientific publications, as seen in Table 2.

Table 2: List of scientific journals for publications

Scientific Journals	Targeted Stakeholders
JMIR Research Protocols Journal	Researchers, academia
Journal of Responsible Innovation	Researchers, academia
IEEE Internet of Things Journal	Researchers, academia
IEEE Transactions on Cloud Computing	Researchers, academia
Journal of Product Innovation Management (JPIM)	Researchers, academia
Science, Technology and Society Journal	Researchers, academia
Health Informatics Journal	Researchers, academia

The consortium must respect Article 29.2 of the Grant Agreement with regards to "Open access to scientific publications", which states that "*Each beneficiary must ensure open access (free of charge online access for any user) to all peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to its results*".

3.6 Events Database

An important part of the VITALISE dissemination and communication strategy is sourced on the real-life, interactive actions that can engage target audiences with the project. In conjunction with the above tools and channels, VITALISE is going to be promoted to the community of its stakeholders through participation in conferences, workshops and other events organised by third parties. Such events offer a significant opportunity for VITALISE to be disseminated in environments where key stakeholders are gathered. Hence, it is valuable for the project's development and impact to participate in events organised by international agencies, fora and institutions which present an expertise around the same scientific domain. Apart from conferences and workshops, which constitute the main types of events by third parties, project partners can also take part in varying events, like networking events, symposia and/or even webinars.

This part of dissemination and communication strategy depends on the good practices between project partners in terms of inner-project communication. That is, partners can share information they receive about upcoming events that present a subject closeness to VITALISE's activities, thus updating the consortium about new dissemination and networking possibilities. Communicating such information can result to partners assisting other partners and collaboratively boost the project's impact on the projected areas of stakeholders.

The consortium has already drafted a preliminary list of potential events that can be targeted for disseminating the project's results, as seen in Table 3.

Table 3: VITALISE preliminary events database

Type of Event	Event	Targeted Stakeholders
Conferences, Workshops & Events	ENoLL Digital Living Lab Days (annual Summit) +Learning Lab Day	LL researchers/innovators, academia, science communicators, policymakers
	Living Labbers Webinars (monthly >150 participants per webinar)	LL researchers/innovators, academia
	EIT Health Summit (annually >700 participants)	Healthcare experts, innovators, researchers, policymakers
	Plénière Forum LLSA (annual Summit)	LL researchers/innovators
	ACM Conference on Knowledge Discovery & Data Mining (annual international forum)	Researchers, academia, innovators, policymakers
	EIP on AHA Conference of Partners (annual summit)	Policymakers, innovators, healthcare experts, science communicators, researchers
	IHE Europe Connectathon Week (annual conference)	Researchers, healthcare experts, innovators, policymakers, science communicators
	EU JRC - SMARTER Conference on Smart Specialisation and Territorial Development (annually)	Researchers, academia, innovators, policymakers
	Open Science Days Conference (annual or biennial)	Researchers, academia, science Communicators, general public
	EuroScience Open Forum (ESOF) (biennial)	Researchers, academia, innovators, policymakers, science communicators
	European Researchers' Night (annual)	Researchers, academia, science Communicators, general public

3.7 Community of stakeholders

It is considered crucial for the long-term viability and the exploitation of VITALISE to establish a communication channel with the policy makers and the general public. Within the framework of Task 13.4 "Awareness towards the general public and policy makers", VITALISE partners will implement a set of actions to setup and maintain an active community of stakeholders including policy makers

that will support the validation of the project outcomes and their innovation and sustainability potential and thus will actively contribute to enrich them.

The task involves all activities for shaping the VITALISE external community that will participate in the development process through the provision of feedback. Except for the general dissemination activities, the task involves the organization of yearly events for presenting VITALISE to key policy makers in Europe.

Linking this task with Task 13.3, VITALISE “Innovation Monitoring Systems” is also a business intelligence tool for policy makers to design forthcoming EU-funded collaborative research & innovation programmes. Disseminating the results of the VITALISE Innovation Monitoring Systems and making them open to the public will help to bridge innovators in research projects and external stakeholders, such as – but not limited to – citizens, investors, technology scouts and incubators.

3.8 Network of Researchers

An essential part of the VITALISE Dissemination and Communication Plan is to prepare the right messages, channels, and tools to attract new researchers willing to use the Living Lab services and procedures. Within the framework of Task 13.2 “Outreach of new researchers” an integrated plan on how to reach those new researchers will be deployed, including all the dissemination and communication activities targeted to creating awareness to new researchers about the provision of access to VITALISE services.

The dissemination activities targeting new researchers evolve mostly around networking techniques, and, more specifically, new researchers will be approached through:

- participation and announcements in scientific conferences and scientific papers
- announcements in popular mailing lists
- collaboration with a wide range of research institutes across Europe.

The dissemination activities will target the complete healthcare scientific community, including SMEs and applied areas of research. The aim is to develop a network of researchers interested in VITALISE activities and to assist them in using the provided services.

The successful outreach will be estimated via the number of researchers that will be part of this network of researchers, as well as the count of the transnational proposals for realization of experimental protocols. The transnational research groups that will receive access via this scheme, acquiring access to infrastructure not available in their region will be independently estimated. This call will promote equal opportunities in the access and take into account the gender dimension when defining the support provided to users. In addition to this, several researchers and industry representatives provided letters of intent for collaboration with the integrated VITALISE, ensuring sufficient demand.

3.9 Synergies

An essential part of VITALISE project’s “Dissemination and Communication Plan” is to establish synergies and natural links with other Horizon 2020 EU-funded projects and relevant initiatives. Networking activities foster a culture of co-operation between research infrastructures, scientific communities, industries and other stakeholders as appropriate, help the development of a more efficient and attractive European Research Area. Synergies will assist the communication of the VITALISE actions to more researchers, as well as assist the capacity building activities described in WP4 “NA3 - Capacity Building and Training” and outreach to new users within the framework of WP11 “NA4 - Calls for ideas and proposals, experiment selection”. Hence, project partners will take part in seminars and conferences organised by the European Commission or other EC funded projects (participation in Horizon 2020 and other EC events) and will try to exploit corresponding synergies.

VITALISE partners have been engaged in various projects that can provide expertise and synergies to the consortium. Laurea CCO project has developed a governance, business and capacity building

model (CCO), to be experimented in health and wellbeing projects in Uusimaa and internationally. AUTH, WITA, SIT have also worked together in the UNCAP project to create technology solutions for older adults. CERTH will re-use and integrate in VITALISE platform the semantic interoperability models for sensor, image, audio, ADLs and clinical profile knowledge developed in FP7 ICT IP Dem@Care. The know-how and infrastructure for large-scale and long-term Living Lab studies, as well as the established network will be activated for VITALISE.

Consortium members will constantly try to get in touch with other relevant projects and initiatives in order to gain knowledge, create awareness and investigate any potential available for common activities and cooperation among them, in a “win-win” perspective. Similar projects in which VITALISE partners already participate or are going to, may comprise a first pool of projects for possible synergies, since there will be an already established contact/ bond. Table 4 is a preliminary list drafted by the consortium, including relevant projects.

Table 4: Preliminary list of projects related to VITALISE

Project	Direct relation to VITALISE
CAPTAIN, H2020, 2017-2020 (www.captain-eu.org). CAPTAIN develops technologies to support people inside their homes as they age, implementing a user- centered co-design philosophy.	AUTH (co-ordinator), INTRAS, SIT, VICOM, NIV will bring experience in combination of user active participatory approaches and the implementation of Software co-development with special emphasis in end-user’s active involvement.
SHAPES, H2020, 2019-2023 (www.shapes2020.eu) 20MEUR Horizon 2020 project that seeks to develop a digital service ecosystem to help ageing people continue to live in their homes.	LAUREA, AUTH, VICOM are partners in SHAPES. The service design, co-creation, ecosystem modelling and substantive competence in the well-being of the ageing population will be valuable to VITALISE.
ProVaHealth, INTERREG Baltic Sea Region, 2017-2019 (www.scanbalt.org/livinglabs/provahealth/) ProVaHealth facilitates access to health infrastructures for startups and SMEs.	LAUREA One of the project outcomes is the Transnational Living Lab concept including a service model.
EIT HEALTH Living Labs & test Beds Project, 2016-2020 (www.eithealth.eu/project/living-labs-and-test-beds). The program encourages Living Labs and test beds to join the network.	LLSA, UPM will involve the EIT Health Living Labs and Test Beds as well as co-piloting the activities in this ecosystem, contributing directly to VITALISE.
CrossCare, Interreg VL-NL, 2016-2021 (www.crosscare.eu). CrossCare accelerates implementation of care innovations by offering combined Living Lab services from 7 care testing grounds and has a fund to support innovation projects.	LiCalab leads the project: 7 Living Labs and 65 companies & care organizations are involved in co-creation and live testing of medical devices and assisted living products. The experience captured in the project contributes to the methodology of cross border collaboration of Living Labs.
ACTIVAGE, H2020-IOT-2016, 2017–2020 (www.activageproject.eu). ACTIVAGE unifies seven EU IoT platforms (FIWARE, universAAL, OpenIoT etc.) and provides Active and Healthy Ageing (AHA) applications.	CERTH, UPM will provide VITALISE with the knowledge gained in the implementation of a large- scale pilot with more than 7.000 users. The direct relation with VITALISE resides in providing the expertise about smart living environments.

Furthermore, VITALISE has already identified potential complementary synergies with relevant ESFRI (European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures). More specifically, the European Infrastructure for Translational Medicine (EATRIS) provides fast, tailored access to cutting-edge enabling technologies in translational research and the European Clinical Research Infrastructure Network (ECRIN) that facilitates multinational clinical research. VITALISE thematic network can build

complementary collaboration with these networks that will benefit both sides, valorising the user-centred approach and focus on patients needs in the operation and development of medical technologies, in the piloting, evaluation and user acceptance assessment.

Lastly, VITALISE targets “INFRAIA-02-2020: Integrating Activities for Starting Communities” and addresses its specific challenges aiming to establish synergies and exploit transnational collaboration opportunities through innovative Joint Research Activities. Through the strong network that ENoLL, EIT Health Living Labs and Forum LLSA bring, VITALISE looks for a roadmap to create synergies with relevant or complementary research infrastructures. Their radar on world-class research infrastructures have already brought synergies with the European Commission's science and knowledge service (Joint Research Centre - JRC). The EIT Health Living Labs network aims to promote, improve and add value to the challenges of innovation of products and services in the health and health sectors, support innovation processes in the most relevant segments of the market and enhance the chances of success in innovation. To do so, it contains as part of the network some research infrastructures, so it synergizes with these infrastructures immediately all across Europe.

3.10 Events organised by the project

VITALISE aims to establish networking activities, to foster a culture of co-operation between research infrastructures, scientific communities, industries and other stakeholders as appropriate, and to help develop a more efficient and attractive European Research Area.

Hands-on workshop, hackathons and jam days, organized during the Digital Living Lab Days conference or as satellite events, are some of the activities planned to attract young researchers and students. Summer schools, education material and programs will be implemented both for young researchers and for new-coming Living Labs. All these education activities will be designed and run based on ISO 9001:2015. Medical Physics Lab, AUTH is highly experienced in producing high quality educational material and programs while Forum LLSA has developed partnership with its University members to propose education sessions.

The publication of Joint Research Activities protocols in the clinicaltrials.gov and the JMIR research protocols journal, will increase transparency and scientific validity of the conducted research, which in turn will foster a culture of wider collaboration among the researchers and the VITALISE community.

VITALISE reinforces partnership with industry by means of transferring knowledge and common activities to foster the use of Living Lab research infrastructures by industrial researchers and companies RnD departments. Researchers from SMEs have an ongoing collaboration with many VITALISE Living Labs in order to test and improve their products. This type of collaboration and research exploitation scheme has already been identified as a sustainability goal of ENoLL and is widely adopted by EIT Health Living Labs and Forum LLSA. Forum LLSA has implemented the reference model of Innovation process in Health and Wellbeing domain including research, but also industry. The VITALISE starting community boosts the potential of Living Labs as industry and research testbeds by providing a sound business plan that would exhibit and maintain the Living Labs' value and sustainability beyond the end of the project.

Furthermore, in order to provide high quality procedures and services to researchers, VITALISE will organise the Harmonization Board and Body meetings (T2.2) that will be held every 6 months. There, VITALISE Living Labs and other Health and Wellbeing Living Labs, will exchange with external researchers on their needs and improvements to be done in order to create standards, thus updating the previous version. This activity is considered as an important step to increase trust among Living Lab research infrastructures, the scientific community and industry while at the same time improving the quality of provided procedures and services. Harmonization Board and Body meetings will be adopted by ENoLL and more specifically by the Health and Wellbeing Action Oriented Task Force of ENoLL as a tool, beyond the project duration.

Lastly within the framework of Task 13.4 “Awareness towards the general public and policy makers”, VITALISE partners will implement a set of activities for shaping the VITALISE external community that will participate in the development process through the provision of feedback.

Except for the general dissemination activities, the task involves the organization of yearly events for presenting VITALISE to key policy makers in Europe.

Table 5: List of events organised by VITALISE Consortium

Events organised by VITALISE Consortium		
Networking activities	Meetings with stakeholders	Separate meetings will be conducted with stakeholders in order to gather appropriate feedback and document it to well-defined requirements.
	Utilising partners' networks	The networks of the already existing communities of the consortium partners, with a special focus on the ENoLL (150 members), the EIT Health network (56) and LLSA Forum (60 members) networks.
	Harmonization Board and Body meetings	Face to face meetings in order to share a common understanding of the provided services.
Events organisation	Hands-on workshop, hackathons and jam days during the Digital Living Lab Days conference, as satellite events	2 large scale workshops will be organised.
	Summer schools	3 summer schools with a total of 50 young researchers joining
	Acceleration Bootcamps	50 researchers joining

Table 5 summarises all the events that VITALISE consortium is going to organise within the framework of its communication strategy.

3.11 VITALISE Advisory Board

The VITALISE Advisory Board (AB) is composed of members, outside the project, being senior researchers, Living Lab managers, entrepreneurs and decision makers with a high reputation in the project domain. The AB will be informed on the project results and progress at regular intervals by peer review of selected deliverables. It will meet twice in the course of the project duration to provide suggestions with respect to the project strategic orientations, project research challenges, business and exploitation direction and project support of user needs. The AB members will sign appropriate confidential agreement prior to any disclosure of confidential information.

Among the tasks of the members of the Advisory Board, which are related to the dissemination and communication of VITALISE project, will be to:

- participate in consortium meetings/wider public events organised by the consortium partners, and in these events to link VITALISE to other European and international research initiatives;
- act on opportunities to communicate the results of the project.

Zsuzsanna Bodi who is former Association Director and was leading the ENoLL Office will be one of the primary members of AB. She has 10+ years' experience as Project manager. She has led a team of 16 people in multinational environment, developed business strategy studies and also participated in several national and European projects.

4 Summary of dissemination actions

An integrated communication strategy has been designed and launched by the consortium utilizing a variety of instruments to communicate the project's success stories along with the overall framework within which it is implemented and funded in terms that can be easily understood by the target audience members and by the general public. Dissemination actions will complement the project's dissemination and exploitation activities by providing universally comprehensible information to the public at large regarding the project's goals and results thus increasing the visibility of VITALISE and the project's contribution towards accessible research infrastructures.

This will be achieved by communicating tangible results and pilot success stories coming from the project's JRAs and stimulating positive emotions through the demonstration of the project's activities. The following table shows the planned communication activities, as well as the objectives to evaluate the success of the dissemination and communication strategy.

Table 6: VITALISE Specific communication measures and targets

Objective	Actions required	Result indicator
Create the project's graphical identity	Development of the project logo	1 original logo
	Graphical design of the information brochures and posters	Year 1: At least 1 brochure and 1 poster will be developed in partner languages plus English. Year 2 and Year 3: Update of the materials according to the progress of the project.
	Graphical design of the project website	The project's website will be designed according to the latest UI standards.
	Design the documents and the presentations templates	About 4 templates for project documents, reports, and presentations.
Create the project's online identity	VITALISE website	Year 1: 250 monthly visits Year 2: 500 monthly visits Year 3: 750+ monthly visits
	VITALISE blog	Year 1: 1 blog post per month
		Year 2 and Year 3: at least 2 blog posts per month Associated with document Ref. Ares(2021)1788895 12/03/2021 Blog posts will be published on a constant basis to present and discuss research findings etc, with contributions by all partners
	VITALISE twitter account	Year 1: At least one post per week and 500 followers on Twitter, 300 Likes on Facebook and 100 followers on LinkedIn
	VITALISE LinkedIn group	Year 2: At least two posts per week (700 followers on twitter, 500 Likes on Facebook and 300 followers on LinkedIn) Year 3: At least two posts per week (1000 followers on twitter,
	VITALISE Facebook account	700 Likes on Facebook and 500 followers on LinkedIn)
	VITALISE SlideShare channel	The project's overall presentation will be uploaded on M2 and will be updated every six months. All other open presentations developed by the partnership will also be uploaded.

	VITALISE project videos	The development of the “visual presentation” of the project in the form of a video will be ready on month 12. The video will be used to promote the VITALISE project. On Year 3 the VITALISE product video will be available that will include information about the VITALISE community with the aim to enhance the sustainability of this community.
Document materials about the results of the project	Scientific publications	10 scientific publications in scientific journals or conferences.
	Publication of Joint Research Activities protocols	3 publications in the JMIR Research Protocols, describing the research protocol for each of the 3 Joint Research Activities
	Reports	6 technical reports. One technical report every six months will be available on the project’s website.
	Newsletters	6 newsletters will be prepared during the project. A database with partners’ and associate partners’ contacts of target groups will be created. Circulating the project newsletter will guarantee target groups are reached not only within the partners’ network but also within a larger community of interested potential users. It will include news and upcoming events, publications and report project’s achievements. Also, the project will seek regular presence in the already established ENoLL, EIT Health, Forum LLSA newsletters (>4,000 unique subscribers in total).
	Press releases	2 press releases per partner, regarding the VITALISE development and exploitation will be published in printed and/or electronic media.
	Material and educational programs	Number of educational or training programs >8 (18 hours in total).
Establish networking activities	Participations in conferences, workshops, trade fairs, exhibitions Horizon 2020 and other EC events	30 such interventions are foreseen during the project’s lifetime.
	Meetings with stakeholders	Separate meetings will be conducted with stakeholders in order to gather appropriate feedback and document it to well-defined requirements.
	Synergies with other projects	10 synergies are targeted.
	Utilising partners’ networks	The networks of the already existing communities of the consortium partners, with a special focus on the ENoLL (150 members), the EIT Health network (56) and LLSA Forum (60 members) networks.
	Harmonization Board and Body meetings	Face to face meetings in order to share a common understanding of the provided services.
Organise events	Hands-on workshop, hackathons and jam days during the Digital Living Lab Days conference, as satellite events	2 large scale workshops will be organised.
	Summer schools	3 summer schools with a total of 50 young researchers joining
	Acceleration Bootcamps	50 researchers joining

5 Monitoring and Evaluation

VITALISE elaborates a specific evaluation strategy to monitor its dissemination and communication efforts. The goal is to provide concrete evidence about the effectiveness of the Dissemination and Communication Plan, as well as insights on how to amplify its reach and impact. The periodic review and update of the project's strategy depends on the data sourced in the dissemination and communication reports.

To this end, VILABS as the leader of WP13 is responsible for overseeing the progress of the overall VITALISE dissemination and communication activities. The monitoring and evaluation tools will assess the efforts in both qualitative and quantitative fashion. The procedures to be implemented are the following:

- **Action plan creation and communication inside the consortium.** A specific list of activities will concentrate all the projected dissemination and communication actions which partners have to undertake. This list will comprise pre-defined and scheduled tasks, but it will also include partners individual plans for dissemination and communication activities which due to their nature cannot be precisely pre-organised, like the participation to upcoming conferences and networking events. This database will organise the activities on their whole in order for each partner to know what they are supposed to do and when. In addition, based on this inclusive schedule partners will receive bimonthly updates by VILABS about their dissemination and communication tasks.
- **Dissemination and communication activities reporting by all partners.** When an opportunity for a dissemination activity emerges partners should notify WP13 leader (VILABS) and the coordinator (ENoLL) about it. The dissemination manager will document such action accordingly and provide any necessary assistance (e.g., guidelines, tips for better communication etc.). What is more, upon the completion of any form of their assigned dissemination activity, partners have to report the activity on the online [VITALISE Dissemination Activities Report](#) tool so that a robust tracking of dissemination and communication efforts is made. More information about the online reporting tool can be found in Chapter 5.1 "Monitoring procedure: Reporting and Feedback".
- **Monitoring of participation in events.** As mentioned above activities within the dissemination and communication framework will be carefully evaluated in order to ensure the best possible dissemination of the project. Examples of such monitoring include guidelines to participating partners to inform them on how to communicate VITALISE (tips for photos taken from events, VITALISE posters, brochures, etc.) and/or assistance with presentations preparation.
- **Statistics of visibility, traffic, reach and engagement rates of VITALISE's website and social media platforms.** This will allow partners to better understand the most appropriate timing, communication style and target audience of each message. Furthermore, such metrics are essential for planning re-adjustments.

To produce an accurate monitoring and evaluation procedure, as well as to recognise the impact of the actions carried out, it is essential for all partners to register the activities that they implement on time and correctly. Therefore:

- All partners should prepare their dissemination and exploitation activities according to their personalised action plan;
- All partners should report every dissemination and communication activity they are implementing or contributing to on time by registering them in the online dissemination reporting tool (<https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/vitalisedissreport>);
- All partners should save enough evidence of the completed activities;
- A monitoring tool with the planned and the target activities is used by WP13 leader.

5.1 Monitoring procedure: Reporting and Feedback

The VITALISE Dissemination Activities Report is an online tool used by all consortium partners to report and keep track of the dissemination and communication activities that have been implemented throughout the project. The dissemination reporting tool is available online and can be accessed through the following link: <https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/vitalisedisreport>.

All VITALISE consortium partners need to report any dissemination and communication activity they implement to the online reporting tool. The types of dissemination activities that VITALISE partners could potentially engage with are:

- Organisation of a Workshop or a Networking event
- Participation to a Workshop
- Participation to a Conference
- Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop (Networking events, Exhibitions, Symposia, Webinars etc.)
- Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects (Synergies)
- Training Session
- Press release
- Newsletter
- Scientific and peer reviewed publication (article and/or papers and/or presentation)
- Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication) (Blog entries)
- Media Publications (News pieces, articles etc.)
- Poster
- Flyer
- Social Media
- Website
- Video/Film
- Other

The dissemination reporting is an internal process among consortium partners that the WP13 leader will use in order to:

- Feed the project website with information about the reported activities
- Share the reported information through the project social media (Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, Instagram, YouTube)
- Analyse the information to extract statistics and conclusions that will publish on a frequent basis to the Consortium in order to monitor the progress and take any mitigating actions if needed.
- The reporting should take place at least on a monthly basis. In case it is urgent to publish a particular activity, partners may contact the WP13 leader via email.

Figure 14 is a screenshot of how the VITALISE [Dissemination Activities Report](#) appears online.

Save a backup on your local computer (disable if you are using a public/shared computer)

VITALISE Dissemination Activities Report

Fields marked with * are mandatory.

Disclaimer ✕

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* Name(s) and/or Affiliation(s)

* Type of activity

- Organisation of a Workshop or a Networking event
- Participation to a Workshop
- Participation to a Conference
- Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop (Networking events, Exhibitions, Symposia, Webinars etc.)
- Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects (Synergies)
- Training Session
- Press release
- Newsletter
- Scientific and peer reviewed publication (article and/or papers and/or presentation)
- Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication) (Blog entries)
- Media Publications (News pieces, articles etc.)
- Poster
- Flyer
- Social Media
- Website
- Video/Film
- Other

* Title of activity / slogan

Title of the event (if applicable)

Venue (if applicable)

* Date

Title of the presentation (if applicable)

URL of the activity (if applicable)

URL of the publication (if applicable)

Type of audience reached below. Please select more than one type ONLY if applicable, up to a maximum of 3.
 Please indicate ESTIMATED no of persons reached per type of audience (EC request)

	Industry	Medical Organisations	Research Community	Policy Makers	Society (Customers, Civil groups, general public)	Media	Other
No. of persons	<input style="width: 100%;" type="text"/>	<input style="width: 100%;" type="text"/>	<input style="width: 100%;" type="text"/>				

Please copy below any relevant links (e.g. to videos, presentation files, announcement screenshots, etc.)

Please upload any photos relevant material (e.g. videos, presentation files, announcement screenshots, etc.)

Comments

Figure 14: VITALISE Dissemination Activities Report

5.2 VITALISE Guide on Dissemination and Communication

This informal guide acts as a reminder checklist for partners to contribute to the project's Dissemination and Communication Plan during the whole project duration. It will be crosschecked by the coordinator (ENoLL) and the dissemination leader (VILABS) during every partners' meeting where a relevant presentation of dissemination activities will take place.

The VITALISE dissemination and communication guide is comprised of the below enlisted guidelines, according to which project partners should:

1. Report on the online [Dissemination Activities Report](#) tool (or briefly via email to ENoLL and VILABS) any dissemination or communication activity related to VITALISE, e.g., presentation, publication, participation in events, etc.
2. Inform ENoLL and VILABS about relevant events, where VITALISE partners could participate (e.g., Conferences, Seminars etc.), so that the events database can be regularly updated. If necessary, arrangements could be made so that VITALISE will be represented.
3. Collect photos, videos, from all VITALISE activities (full documentation): meetings, workshops, seminars, press conferences, etc. Send them to ENoLL and VILABS to be used in publicity materials (e.g., project newsletters, videos, etc.). Make sure that there are no third party-intellectual property rights.
4. Use in all of their communication materials (deliverables, presentations, newsletters, etc.) the VITALISE logo, the EU flag and the statement "This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101007990".
5. To avoid conflicts, co-ordinate with other partners and inform ENoLL on intentions to publish from VITALISE. Always mention the financing body (EU / Horizon 2020).
6. Invite local policy makers in appropriate projects stages and inform them on project's progress. Record events (videos - photos). Send them to ENoLL and VILABS.
7. Forward press releases, newsletters and other materials to their contacts that might be interested to VITALISE's objectives and thematic interests.
8. Feel free to contribute to VITALISE website's blog with an article about their work in the project, the progress, etc.
9. Feel free to provide material for regularly updating the VITALISE website.
10. Follow VITALISE's social media pages (Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, LinkedIn, YouTube). Monitor the announcements and posts, "like" them, comment on them. Make their own posts on VITALISE's social media accounts. Connect with people. Initiate the dialogue or take part in it.

Appendices

Appendix 1: VITALISE first press release

Virtual Health and Wellbeing Living Lab Infrastructure H2020 VITALISE project kicks off

On the 1st of April 2021 the Horizon 2020 VITALISE project (<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101007990>) officially kicked off. The full name of the 3-years duration project is “Virtual Health and Wellbeing Living Lab Infrastructure” and it was recently approved for funding in the frame of the Horizon 2020 European Research Programme (call topic “Integrating and opening research infrastructures of European interest”).

VITALISE aims to **harmonize Living Lab procedures** and **open Living Lab Infrastructures** as a means to facilitate and promote research activities in the **Health and Wellbeing domain** in Europe and beyond. Transnational access to 17 Living Lab research infrastructures and remote digital access to datasets (Virtual Access) will be offered to external researchers from all disciplines through three open calls starting from next year. External researchers will have the opportunity to conduct part of their study in rehabilitation, transitional care and everyday life activities or any other domain by visiting the VITALISE living labs. VITALISE will design and develop **ICT tools** for shared access of similar devices and applications used across Living Labs, as well as for collecting, storing and sharing datasets. VITALISE will also invest in the development of **Training** methods towards the wider understanding and valorisation of Living Lab methodologies in the research community.

By bringing together three networks, [ENoLL](#), [Forum LLSA](#), and [EIT Health Living Labs](#), VITALISE interconnects the majority of Living Labs across Europe to cover all European geographical areas and all the spectrum of the Health and Wellbeing domain.

Coordinated by ENoLL, the VITALISE consortium consists of 19 partners from 11 countries, with excellent experience in all the tasks defined for VITALISE. In particular, the partners provide the project with scientific (AUTH, LAUREA, LICALAB, VICOM, CERTH, AIT, UPM, SLIMMER, McGill, UDEM), technical (AUTH, VICOM, CERTH, UPM, WITA, VILABS), policy making (ENoLL, LAUREA, UPM, LLSA, SLIMMER), Living Labs methodologies (ENoLL, AUTH, LAUREA, INTRAS, TREBAG, GAIA, AIT, UPM, LLSA, SLIMMER, McGill, UDEM), innovation and exploitation (SIT, VILABS, AV) experience.

Non-partner Living Labs can be involved in the harmonization process. How? You can join all **knowledge sharing events on Living Lab procedures and services** (workshops, interviews, questionnaires) and you can **participate in the Harmonization Body meetings** (bottom-up approach for standards creation, new standard every six months, new open tools to facilitate procedures and services). Let us all learn from each other and collaborate for shaping the future of Living Labs in research.

To learn more about our project you can visit our [website](#) and you can [subscribe](#) to our newsletter.

Key facts

Starting date: 1/4/2021

Duration: 36 months

Online presence

<https://vitalise-project.eu>

[@VITALISEproject](#)

D13.1 Dissemination and Communication Plan

EC funding: €4,999,262.50

[@VITALISEproject](#)

19 partners / 11 EU countries

[VITALISE Project](#)

Project coordinator: Dr. Evdokimos Konstantinidis (info@vitalise-project.eu)